

Erratum to 'Identification and Quantification of Hazardous Scenarios for Automated Driving'

Birte Kramer¹, Christian Neurohr¹, Matthias Bker², Eckard Bde¹, Martin Frnzle¹, and Werner Damm¹

¹ OFFIS, Oldenburg, Germany

{kramer,neurohr,boede,franzle,damm}@offis.de

² BTC Embedded Systems, Oldenburg, Germany
matthias.bueker@btc-es.de

1 Introduction

In this document we report and correct erroneous parts within our publication 'Identification and Quantification of Hazardous Scenarios for Automated Driving' [2]. The erroneous formulae are to be found in the quantification part of the method, in particular

- Section 4, Step (6), equations in (3) and (4),
- Section 4, Step (7), equations in (1) and (2).

Let us mention that the errors could be corrected and do not affect the validity of the proposed method for quantification of hazardous scenarios that has been presented in [2, Section 4].

2 Notation and Assumptions

As to make this erratum for comprehensible, we repeat the notation and formalization of assumptions from [2] in greater detail. An environmental condition (EC) is denoted by c_i and a sub-scenario $Z_j \subset Z$ where $i = 1, \dots, m$ and $j = 1, \dots, n$, such that

$$Z_j = \bigcap_{i \in I_j} c_i \quad (1)$$

for an index set I_j associated with the sub-scenario Z_j , $j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. Moreover, let $e_1 \geq P(c_1), \dots, e_m \geq P(c_m)$ denote upper bounds for the probability of occurrence of the ECs. Under the assumption that the ECs c_i are **stochastically independent** (1) implies that

$$P(Z_j) = P\left(\bigcap_{i \in I_j} c_i\right) = \prod_{i \in I_j} P(c_i) \leq \prod_{i \in I_j} e_i. \quad (2)$$

Further, we formalize the assumption that the sub-scenarios **cover Z exhaustively** as

$$Z \subseteq \bigcup_{j=1}^n Z_j.$$

3 Erroneous Formulae

3.1 Section 4, Step (6), (3)

The formula [2, Section 4, Step (6), (3)] is **incorrect**:

$$P(H|Z_j) \leq \prod_{i \in I_j} \mu_i P(c_i).$$

We introduced the error rates μ_i in order to represent the probability that an EC (an event outside of the system) leads to a derivation from correct service (an error) inside the system. In the case of the proposed environment fault trees (EFT), the leaves of the fault tree are the ECs and their parents are errors in the perception of the AD system. However, an error may not always directly lead to a hazard. If we name D_i the deviation caused by c_i then we have that

$$\mu_i = P(D_i|c_i).$$

Therefore, the μ_i encode the resilience of the perception components against ECs. Thus, the **correct formula** for [2, Section 4, Step (6), (3)] is given by

$$P(H|Z_j) \leq \prod_{i \in I_j} \mu_i. \quad (3)$$

The inequality in (3) (rather than equality) stems from the fact that other error rates unequal to one could exist, higher up in the fault tree. For sake of simplicity we omitted the inclusion of all these error rates, which is equivalent to setting them all equal to one.

3.2 Section 4, Step (6), (4)

The formula [2, Section 4, Step (6), in (4)] is **incorrect**:

$$P(H \cap Z) = P(Z)P(H|Z) \leq P(Z) \sum_{j=1}^n P(H|Z_j) \leq P(Z) \sum_{j=1}^n \prod_{i \in I_j} \mu_i e_i. \quad (4)$$

Instead, we provide the following **correct formula**:

$$\begin{aligned} P(H \cap Z) &\leq P(H \cap \bigcup_{j=1}^n Z_j) = P(\bigcup_{j=1}^n (H \cap Z_j)) \\ &\leq \sum_{j=1}^n P(H \cap Z_j) = \sum_{j=1}^n P(H|Z_j)P(Z_j) \\ &\stackrel{(2)}{=} \sum_{j=1}^n P(H|Z_j) \prod_{i \in I_j} P(c_i) \stackrel{(2),(3)}{\leq} \sum_{j=1}^n \prod_{i \in I_j} \mu_i e_i. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

3.3 Section 4, Step (7), (1)

As a result of the error reported in (4), the formula in [2, Section 4, Step (7), in (1)] is **incorrect**:

$$P(H \cap Z) \leq P(Z) \sum_{j=1}^n P(H|Z_j) \leq p_{\max}.$$

The **correct formula** follows immediately from (5):

$$P(H \cap Z) \leq \sum_{j=1}^n \prod_{i \in I_j} \mu_i e_i \leq p_{\max}. \quad (6)$$

3.4 Section 4, Step (7), (2)

Again, as a result of the error reported in (4), the formulas in [2, Section 4, Step (7), (2)] are **incorrect**:

$$\begin{aligned} \prod_{i \in I_j} \mu_i e_i &= P(H|Z_j) \leq \frac{p_{\max}}{n \cdot P(Z)}, & \text{for } j = 1, \dots, n. \\ \implies \prod_{i \in I_j} \mu_i &\leq \frac{p_{\max}}{n \cdot P(Z) \cdot \prod_{i \in I_j} e_i}, & \text{for } j = 1, \dots, n. \end{aligned}$$

Instead, the **correct formulas**, without the term $P(Z)$ appearing in the denominator on the right hand side, follow from (6):

$$\begin{aligned} \prod_{i \in I_j} \mu_i e_i &\leq \frac{p_{\max}}{n}, & \text{for } j = 1, \dots, n. \\ \implies \prod_{i \in I_j} \mu_i &\leq \frac{p_{\max}}{n \cdot \prod_{i \in I_j} e_i}, & \text{for } j = 1, \dots, n. \end{aligned}$$

4 Conclusion

The corrections provided in this erratum simplify the corresponding equations of subsection 3.2, subsection 3.3 and subsection 3.4, as the dependence on the term $P(Z)$ vanishes.

Finally, we thank our industry partners who became aware of the erroneous formulae while applying the proposed method for quantification of hazardous scenarios and contacted us for clearance. Moreover, we corrected the same errors in the corresponding technical report [1].

References

1. Eckard Böde, Matthias Büker, Werner Damm, Martin Fränze, Birte Kramer, Christian Neurohr, and Sebastian Vander Maelen. Identifikation und Quantifizierung von Automationsrisiken für hochautomatisierte Fahrfunktionen. Technical report, OFFIS e.V., 2019.
2. Birte Kramer, Christian Neurohr, Matthias Büker, Eckard Böde, Martin Fränze, and Werner Damm. Identification and quantification of hazardous scenarios for automated driving. In *International Symposium on Model-Based Safety and Assessment*, pages 163–178. Springer, 2020.